

Overview

I show how to quickly map relationships of complex system components using a scenario of a small town of 5,000 facing an Internet outage. Reporting, visualization, and data for the model takes up less space than a medium sized digital image of 2MB. The model does not require experts, servers or administrators to build, share and maintain.

Small and Simple

Over time computer software gets larger and it takes more time to do anything. We wait for systems to boot, connect, update, and process. Third parties hold the knowledge, visualization, and access to our information. This paper turns back time to when an entire model of an organization could fit on a floppy disk, yet still use modern tools like Deno and knowledge graphs for analysis.

Deno ensures code can run on any computer, much like a web browser. It is a free and open source JavaScript runtime environment for macOS, Windows, and GNU/Linux operating systems that abstracts storage and processing in a portable, standard, and efficient way ([“Deno” 2024](#)) . It is distributed as a single binary file that is currently 117MB in size. Deno and web browsers can both use the same standard code and formats to process, store, share, and display data.

Knowledge graphs capture small bits of knowledge in a flexible way that can adapt as we learn more about our systems. They organize components of a system by relationships, and can be visualized like a map. They were used to operate railroads in 1855 ([McCallum 1855](#)) . Knowledge graphs let us build directly from the napkin without losing initial analysis. This paper switches between the scenario narrative and technical details multiple times, as a way to educate, but still engage the reader. No previous technical experience is required to use these ideas, just patience.

Figure 1: Govern

Crisis Scenario

Our scenario starts a half hour after the connectivity is down. If you would like to follow along, the live model and reports are available to view at Triples Pub ([“AA - Model Interactive” n.d.](#)) . Databases, reporting, and office automation for the town are housed on cloud services. Everything has stopped working. Grocery stores are unable to sell product, as many have stopped taking cash. Gas stations aren’t able to order gasoline, as most distributors require online ordering. People are living off of the few days of food supplies that they have in their pantries. This is not meant to replace FEMA maps or similar local guides ([FEMA 2024](#)) . The premise of this paper is that no prior preparation has been done. The town council meets. A quick brainstorming session establishes the priorities in Fig. 1. There is water for now, but it is not clear how to obtain and distribute food. Energy, security, water, food, shelter and medical are delegated to city staff to analyze, while the issues with farming and food are resolved. The first task is to determine who the farmers are and interview them to discover how their distribution works, so that food deliveries can be scheduled.

Figure 2: Food

One of the council staff drives 200 miles to the nearest town not affected by the outage, downloads a copy of the contact list, and loads it into the model. There are 50 people available to capture additional information. See Fig. 11 for the farmer contact list or view the live list online ([“AA - Farmers Report” n.d.](#)) . The farmers on the list are interviewed over old copper pair phone lines or in person, and Fig. 2 is created. Fig. 2 is all within the Food node in Fig. 1. This zoom feature of knowledge graphs allows perspective change from everybody in the town to people directly involved with food distribution. Wheat Link in Fig. 2 is unknown to most townsfolk; however, since farmers are directly involved with food distribution, they are very familiar with it. Collapsing a graph into a node also simplifies the current view. The graph is captured by staff in a simple format called Graph Stack.

Graph Stack Format

Graph Stack Format works sequentially, with the state reset by **:: level!**. The current level sticks until the next level command. Lst. 1 shows how to represent the single connection from Farmers to Distribution in Graph Stack Format. Lst. 2 shows the more cumbersome DOT version ([“DOT. Graphviz” n.d.](#)) .

Listing 1 Graph Stack Format Example

```
:: agents
Farmers
:: transforms
Distribution
:: back
Farmers
```

Listing 2 DOT Format Example

```
digraph {
  rankdir="LR" charset="utf-8"
  graph [fontname="Arial"]
  edge [penwidth="2" color="#009988" fontname="Arial"]
  node [style="filled" penwidth="2" fontname="Arial"]
  "Distribute" -> "Farmers" [dir="back"]
  "Distribute" [id="Distribute" label="Distribute" margin=".01" fillcolor="#ffd6bc"
  ⇐ color="#EE7733" shape="octagon" style="filled"]
  "Farmers" [id="Farmers" label="Farmers" margin=".05" fillcolor="#fff0ec"
  ⇐ color="#CC3311" shape="rectangle" style="filled"]
}
```

The `:: agents` and `:: transforms` commands in Lst. 1 specify the type of nodes on the current level. Since an edge must include a transform, flow only applies to transforms, and is specified by the commands `:: forward`, `:: back`, and `:: both`. The remaining `:: items` command applies to the current flow. All text after `:: items`, and before the next command is a description of the items flowing. The fact that levels reset perspective, means that whatever level you are populating, you can edit at the top of the stack. Modifying the graph works in just one dimension, so it is possible to drag a node on one level to another along the y axis (up and down), but render in two dimensions.

Fig. 3 is a simple set of components (nodes) that can be used to analyze systems and create knowledge graphs of combined material and data flow. Materials are stored in locations. Agents provide operational data to transforms. Transforms modify and move materials. The connection between the nodes are called edges. The Farmers node to Distribution node is a single atom of knowledge, a triple: **Govern agent - operates - Distribute transform**. Materials must flow over edges via transforms. Agents can be computer programs. Humans can be both agents and part of a materials transform. An agent node expands into a data flow, where data flows over the edges instead of materials. Data flow nodes include processes, entities, and datastores. Processes transform data. Entities create or consume data, and data at rest is stored in datastores. I will illustrate with the Plant transform.

Figure 3: Nodes

Plant Transform

A big issue that came up during interviews is that it is close to planting time for the majority of grain crops, and if no seeds are planted, there will be no harvest. Staff are not able to contact farm help, as that is done via third party contracting over the Internet, and is affected by the outage. Farm help plants and harvests the crops, and the farmers do not directly contact the help. The Planting Leads do this over mobile with a cloud app, SMS, and IP text as shown in Fig. 4. The Plant node in Fig. 2 is a transform, operated by Farm Help and Wheat Link, that takes seeds from Farm Storage and plants them in Fields. In order to understand the knowledge behind the Plant transform, we need to zoom into the Plant node. Fig. 4 is the graph behind the Plant transform node. Notice that the transform of Plant has quite a bit of intelligence behind it. Rather than Farm Help, we shift the agent to a more detailed Planters that sow seeds in four fields from Farm Storage. Only data is flowing on the red edges. Materials (seeds) are flowing on the teal edges. Farm Storage is a location for materials, not data. Likewise, the fields are locations that contain soil, water, plants, and seeds. None of the red nodes connected to Planters can connect to the Sow transform connected nodes. An agent has a data flow behind it, as it processes, and stores knowledge for present and future use, that help make operational decisions for transforms.

The meaning is not exact (Vallicella 2009) [1]. It is forced, as Planters is a material flow agent and a data flow entity. We can say that Planters (data flow entity) is the same as Planters (material flow agent). Yes, there are some issues with changed meaning, but a bulldozer approach is good enough for our purposes (Halpin, Herman, and Hayes 2009) [2].

Most of the world of 2024 revolves around a data flow perspective. Material flow is separate, and is rarely visualized in the same graph. We tend to gloss over the material flows like minerals and energy, as though we can simply imagine a new world, and with enough datacenters grinding on the data and primping entertainment and social media feeds, we will manifest that world.

In our scenario, Planters understand what to do based on technology and data flow. The process nodes in Fig. 4, like SMS Text and WL Plant, can have an exploded data flow graph that is a sub-process of the particular process node. This is how multi-level data flow diagrams work. Since the sub-process is within the process node, like its parent, it can only connect to an agent where the node is a descendent of a node that was behind that agent. The data at rest might be a book, a human memory, or a database stored on disk drives. For more background on how data flow works, as well as more information about knowledge graphs, see Triple System Analysis (H. 2023) [3]. I also published a fully functioning three level data flow model ("Data Flow Model" n.d.) [4]. Roles swap back and forth between human agents and machine agents in our scenario as we deal with the crisis. In the real world, machine agents have slowly taken more agency from human agents over the last 60 years.

There are five broken processes in Fig. 4. WL Plant provides reports that Planters use to pull the correct amount of seeds from Farm Storage and register the amount in the Inventory Queen cloud application so the Farmers can resupply. The Seeder AI measures the moisture in the soil, the hardness, and other metrics that help adjust the planting for next year, as well as modify tilling for unplanted fields. The Farmers also review Seeder AI to store the data in Wheat Link. All of these cloud services and remote storage are now unavailable. IP Text, which is used by the Planting Leads to help staff the Planters is not working. The Farmers are adamant that the data be captured for manual entry when the Internet connectivity returns, but it might take six months or more. Inventory Queen Cloud, Seeder AI, and WL Plant need to be replaced temporarily. The planters need knowledge to act as agents planting seeds. They also need to capture the knowledge that the cloud services used to capture. After discussing with the farmers, planting leads, and planters, it was decided that another person needed to be in the field helping with a laptop. The transition knowledge system as a data flow is shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 4: Plant

Figure 5: Planters

Fig. 5 uses Field Aids that measure moisture in the soil, referring to a paper and PDF planting guide that the Farmers write in orchestration with the Planters. The Field Aids enter how many seeds are planted, and communicate the rate needed to the Planters. Every day their laptops are dropped off with the Farmers who consolidate the results, as shown in Fig. 6. This is how they know how much seed and fertilizer they need to purchase, and how to price their crops for market. They are willing to share the cost with the city to deal with the crisis, but want to make sure that they can re-load the data from the interim solution back into their systems. This system does that.

If needed, we could expand any of the processes in Fig. 6 for further detail; however, the Farmers are happy with the plan so far, and with the collaboration between the Field Aids, Planting Lead, Planters and Farmers, it is expected that planting the fields will go just fine, and still capture the data for when the cloud services are available again the following season.

There is another bigger problem, although it isn't quite as pressing as getting the seeds in the ground. Water used to irrigate the crops is affected by the outage, as the dam was retrofitted to cloud control. The issue with the dam is significant, as the flow valves need to be manually adjusted, and the people that used to know how to do it are no longer working there. The Farmers only know what valves to turn on to reroute water for irrigation once it reaches them, so the town council sends staff to the dam to investigate.

Fig. 7 shows how the WL Irrigate agent controls the water flow from the reservoir to the fields, as well as controls the pumping from the 3 dams. It turns out that in addition to adjusting the valves, WL Irrigate monitors the water going into the intake for logs and other items that can jam the pumps, and stops pumping until a clear signal is sent by the Dam workers. They can still do that, but without the cloud service they are not notified, so that needs to be done as well. Unfortunately, there are no spare Dam staff, so the town staff need to take turns at the canal valve and the three dams and adjust the valves as needed via SMS text messages. It requires four permanent positions for two 8 hour shifts with no water flowing from 10PM until 6AM. While WL Irrigate had infrared sensors, there is no equivalent for the human monitors, so the pumps need to be turned off completely at night.

Figure 6: Consolidate

Delegation with knowledge graphs is easy, because no authoritative schema is necessary. If interviews and investigation turn up unknown clusters of relations, they can easily be connected with the broader effort without prior definitions. So far we have had several distinct efforts that can run in parallel. Meanwhile, back at town hall, this information is being gathered and assembled. In our scenario, there are no expectations of technical expertise, so entry methods for the model need to be simple. Fig. 8 shows a UI that can be used to enter and modify knowledge graphs. Rather than arrange nodes in 2D, where you need to deal with crossing lines and other confusing problems, the UI is in 1 dimension, a vertical stack of nodes and operations. The indentation is automatic. In Fig. 8, you can see how the user is dragging the connection between Irrigate and Wheat Link to a two way connection (both).

Lst. 3 shows how to convert Graph Stack Format in Lst. 1 into a diagram. The imported modules are available on Triples Pub (“AA - Libraries” n.d.) [\[link\]](#). While this is written for beginners in mind, I’ll assume that installing Deno and creating a text file with the contents of Lst. 3 is something the audience can do.

Figure 8: Stack

the models in this paper, including all software to maintain and visualize the data of the small town all fit in data the size of a floppy without any other dependencies. Like a floppy, you need a computer to use the data. In this case, though, all that is needed is any computer that can run Deno and Pandoc.

This paper you are reading, along with models and software, is embedded in a single PNG file called a Floppy PNG that literally looks like a floppy (“AA - Floppy PNG for Triples Pub” n.d.) [\[link\]](#). It stores roughly the same amount of data as a floppy, although it can grow to many times the size. Web pages have mediocre protection, since a variety of methods can hijack and interject code. This is similar to problems with a floppy disk. To mitigate this, a Floppy PNG is signed with a private key, and verified with a public key. The methods in this paper are meant to be quick. The town can’t wait for people to be trained. Sharing the entire town model is as simple

Figure 7: Irrigate

The town shares the models with the equivalent of a floppy disk. While the floppy disk is increasingly foreign to most users, there are characteristics that are useful, even today. Primarily, it is possible to take a floppy disk with you, and share information without relying on third parties. Cloud, along with complicated data and visualization supply chains have many advantages, like frictionless user experience, but frictionless does not mean simple or portable. Students and others that couldn’t afford a computer, could simply pack around some floppy disks, and use commodity computing. Modern cloud architectures make that kind of independence difficult. We have many interconnected services instead, with most charging a fee. At the same time, the technology we have developed in the last 25 years can provide things within the same utility of the floppy disk that are astounding to present-day IT consumers. The

as texting a 2MB image. This doesn't require training. There is no need for complicated storage solutions, and it is easy to replicate. True, it is important to back up the model and track versions; however, there is another advantage to the way that information is stored. The same reason that allows delegation and parallel efforts, is the reason that versioning isn't a big problem. The technical term for the problem is locking. The methods in this paper lock on an atom of knowledge, a triple.

Listing 3 Deno GFS Conversion

```
import { n_s, model_to_dots } from './text-model-dot.js'
await import('./hpcc-js-graphviz.js')
var gv = await window['@hpcc-js/wasm'].Graphviz.load()
const hd=`digraph {
  rankdir="LR" charset="utf-8"
  graph [fontname="Arial"]
  edge [penwidth="2" color="#009988" fontname="Arial"]
  node [style="filled" penwidth="2" fontname="Arial"]`
const model=`:: level
Top
:: agents
Govern
:: transforms
Distribute
:: back
Govern`
Deno.writeFileSync('example.svg',
gv.dot(hd+Object.values(model_to_dots(model, {})).dots.Top).join('\n')+}')`
```

Lst. 4 works cross-platform to extract the bootstrap from a Floppy PNG. The bootstrap is always on the second PNG scan line. The metadata JSON is on the first line. This means that even if nobody can be reached to help, any data that is shared with a Floppy PNG can be used and the system/visualization operated. Put pigz in the current directory, or make sure it is in the path and remove the ".". For Windows this works fine in a Power Shell shell. I've created several different models, and all of them use build.js with an option of generate to create all of the files, resources, and scripts. An option of maintain will provide a local web server that lets you maintain the model. It is a general feature of Floppy PNGs, and the one created for the small town crisis model in this paper works this way as well.

Listing 4 Deno Extract

```
Deno.writeFileSync("u.z",Deno.readFileSync("z.png").slice(41,-16))
let command=new Deno.Command('./pigz', {args: ["-d","u.z"]})
command.outputSync()
let r=Deno.readFileSync("u").slice(2882,2882+2880).trim()
Deno.writeFileSync("bootstrap.js",r)
```

Maps vs. Streams

This topic is treated more completely in my paper Triple System Analysis (H. 2023) (3SA). In many ways, the entire 3SA paper is about maps vs. streams. In addition to being lightweight, mapped knowledge can have authority behind the triple. Consider the authority behind the ID for a citizen in a country. In the United States, this is the Social Security Number. The triple of that relationship would be: citizen-has_ssn-555 55 5555. This triple has significant importance, and hijacking that relationship is a key part

of identity theft. Simple questions about a system have similar characteristics. In our example of the valve for the dam, everybody that knows how to operate the irrigation valves manually had left. The Dam Corp. Chief Operations Officer made a splash several years earlier by approving the cloud controls. Dam Corp. saved money on insurance, because fewer logs made it into the intake, they could operate 24/7, and they were able to lay off several union positions without running afoul of the existing labor contract. The COO got a pay bump, and everybody left at the Dam was pleased, as were the Farmers. There were fewer interruptions in the flow of irrigation. Until now. When we rely on massive streams of operational data, and apex cloud companies to manage critical knowledge, we risk hijacking and loss of control of knowledge for our own purposes and others (Blumenthal 2024) [\[1\]](#). This doesn't mean that every triple has to have the authority, care, and security behind it of a citizen's ID, but it does mean that certain bits of knowledge should not be ceded easily. This is a core reason for this paper on Adaptive Analysis as well. I am challenging the prevailing attitude that broader system knowledge is too complicated, too difficult to manage, by showing that a reasonably complete model can fit in the space of a floppy disk, with full reporting and visualization of the critical components.

Machine Agent

Fig. 7 has the WL Irrigate agent. Unlike Planters, the agent is entirely machine. Prior to the outage, the Irrigate module of Wheat Link handled the transfer of water via the Pumping and Canal transforms. The Farmers and Dam staff referred to the agent as WLI. Since the previous human operators were laid off, the operation became invisible. It became frictionless. The operation was accounted for as a monthly service. There were no HR or insurance costs to worry about. When the outage happened, everybody still referred to WLI. Because of this, when the town staff mapped out how to get water to the fields and staffed the valves manually, they decided it made more sense to continue to call the agent WLI, even though it was made up of humans. There were further reductions in HR, and even if the Dam Corp wanted to hire human operators again, it would be difficult to do, so the desire, like with the Planters agent, is to move back to cloud services as soon as the outage is over.

Figure 9: WLI

Listing 5 triples

```
[[ "h3d4h6x3", "first_name", "Flavie" ],
 [ "h3d4h6x3", "last_name", "Olson" ],
 [ "h3d4h6x3", "mobile_number", "(555) 737-7734" ],
 [ "h3d4h6x3", "street_address", "4374 Oakfield Road E" ],
 [ "h3d4h6x3", "role", "Farm Lead" ]]
```

How Soon is Now?

As I write this, several generations have looted the biosphere with the aid of oil. I say several, because we were innocent prior to President Lyndon B. Johnson's report ("[White House Report, 'Restoring the](#)

Quality of Our Environment,’ Report of the Environmental Pollution Panel, President’s Science Advisory Committee, November 1965 | National Security Archive” 1965) (Fletcher et al. 2024). I’ve worked on these ideas for five years, with related threads going back to 2006. I have widely shared my concerns about our situation, as well as my conviction that understanding systems at levels of relations > 2 is important for the health of the biosphere. We are human. We need to be loved, yes, but as sons and heirs, we will inherit nothing in the end, because we are unwilling to understand that sun, air, water, and soil, combined with a billion years of harmonious evolution, brought us to this point, and we are not separate (“This Is How Johnny Marr Came up with the How Soon Is Now? Riff. Radio x” 2024) (Vegan_Semih_Cyprus_33 2021). We are the sun. We are the air, and yet we go about things the wrong way, touting our triumphs in ridiculous manifestos (a16z 2023).

I am the nerd. I am the heir. I also was inspired by the freedom of personal computers in the late 1970s and early 1980s (Apple Inc. 2004) (BC Prod. 2022) (“Bill Atkinson Part 2. TWiT.tv” 2016). I believe that there is some level of appropriate technology; however, we need to be willing to put in the work to understand what that level is, and work in good faith to bring balance, to reject being a cancer on the Earth, and leave room for nature (“Georgia Guidestones” 2024). I have close to zero hope that my current culture in 2024 will find these methods useful. This is the main reason for this format of paper and the scenario. Perhaps at varying points on the way down and back up again, if that happens, these methods will be useful (Snyder 1974). Perhaps a small town or organization loses internet connectivity for an extended period of time. These methods inform the broader goal of good faith balance with nature, as well as making our actual needs clear. The lede is buried. It is time to close up this paper.

Closure

At this point in our scenario, town staff are orchestrating the issues with food. Some staff are working valves at the Dams and Canal. Others are working with the field aids to assist with planting. The sun will take over from there. How much of a model is needed right now? The town council decides to let the existing efforts settle and canvas the citizens for other needs. In the mean time the critical reports are available. The most pressing report is Fig. 10, which shows the staff that handles the valves at the Dam.

Liaisons

Name	Street Address	Mobile:	Email Address:
Kulas, Estella	3773 Garden Close SE	(555) 673-6336	Estella.Kulas@example.org
Sawayn, Khalil	6773 W State Street NW	(555) 343-4734	Khalil.Sawayn@example.org
Senger, Salvador	6737 Prospect Road E	(555) 467-3343	Salvador.Senger@example.org
Thompson, Ethan	4444 The Maltings NE	(555) 643-3673	Ethan.Thompson@example.org

Figure 10: Liaisons

They are constantly texting back and forth to staff the valves. When one of them is sick, another must pull multiple shifts. They get overtime, and track hours worked with the Dam timecard entry system, which texts the Town accountant.

The data of the town is stored as triples. A typical citizen is shown in Lst. 5. Unlike in my paper Triple System Analysis, the triples in this model are text stored as an array of arrays, with the subject, predicate, and object as three elements in each; however, the flexibility of triples described in the paper apply (H. 2023). If it makes more sense to use emoji, go for it. For the town model, I use an ID made of alternating letters and numbers, limited to cdfhjknprtxy and 34679. This minimizes verbal and written confusion; for instance, 0 and 0 are excluded as are L and I. 5,000 town members and the graphs so far, as well as all the software to generate the graphs and create the PDF takes a hair over 1MB. There is plenty of room to expand and extend the model. The Graph Stack format doesn’t take much space. The data for all of the graphs so far takes less than 1K compressed. View all townspeople on the online

report (“AA - All Townspeople” n.d.) [🔗](#). I’m using a greenbar format to make viewing easier, which can be seen more clearly in Fig. 11.

Farmers

Name	Street Address	Mobile:	Email Address:
Berge, Abigail	7667 Queen's Road NW	(555) 377-4467	Abigail.Berge@example.org
Bode, Joaquin	4674 Union Street E	(555) 747-7447	Joaquin.Bode@example.org
Boehm, Heath	7636 Elm Grove S	(555) 437-7647	Heath.Boehm@example.org
Bosco, Chandler	3773 E 4th Avenue E	(555) 736-4673	Chandler.Bosco@example.org
Carter, Walter	7367 Oak Drive NW	(555) 446-3643	Walter.Carter@example.org
DuBuque, Willow	4446 W Church Street W	(555) 443-6776	Willow.DuBuque@example.org
Feeney, Zola	4646 Gordon Street SE	(555) 636-4346	Zola.Feeney@example.org
Franey, Quinn	7336 Oxford Street S	(555) 433-4333	Quinn.Franey@example.org
Goyette, Vergie	6464 Manor Gardens E	(555) 747-3443	Vergie.Goyette@example.org
Hackett, Emiliano	6644 N Cedar Street W	(555) 634-6474	Emiliano.Hackett@example.org
Harris, Dianna	7436 N Church Street NW	(555) 747-3673	Dianna.Harris@example.org
Kihn, Marcia	4446 The Green SE	(555) 474-4446	Marcia.Kihn@example.org
Kovacek, Dejah	6747 Commerce Street N	(555) 374-3674	Dejah.Kovacek@example.org
O'Conner, Erik	7476 Martin Luther King Jr Boulevard NE	(555) 444-3434	Erik.O'Conner@example.org
Pouros, Tyrell	6737 Elm Road NE	(555) 667-4337	Tyrell.Pouros@example.org
Predovic, Rigoberto	7373 W Front Street SE	(555) 433-7474	Rigoberto.Predovic@example.org
Schneider, Dorothy	7464 Pearl Street NE	(555) 763-6644	Dorothy.Schneider@example.org
Schumm, Wilson	7467 Albert Road W	(555) 363-4773	Wilson.Schumm@example.org
Treutel, Casper	7664 E 10th Street W	(555) 743-3777	Casper.Treutel@example.org
Upton, Raquel	4444 N 1st Street SE	(555) 366-7737	Raquel.Upton@example.org

Figure 11: Farmers

Running the Model

The tools are isolated from issues with software and material supply chains by a run-time (Dupras 2024) [🔗](#). Modification of the model and documentation is done on all operating systems with Deno, a free, open source run-time without additional dependencies or network connection requirements. (“Deno” 2024) [🔗](#). Pandoc, Pandoc-crossref, and Latex are needed to create PDF documentation (MacFarlane 2024) [🔗](#) (MacFarlane 2020) [🔗](#) (Yakimov 2024) [🔗](#) (TUG 2024) [🔗](#). For **macOS and GNU/Linux**, Rsvg-convert, which comes with the librsvg package, is needed for GNU/Linux. For macOS, use whatever package manager you like, but Homebrew has been tested (Howell 2024) [🔗](#). For **Windows**, Windows 11 has been tested, but lower versions might work as well. Put rsvg-convert and pandoc-crossref in the Pandoc directory (Miyako 2024) [🔗](#). By default, this is in **Windows\Program Files\Pandoc** . To extract the bootstrap from the PNG Floppy, you’ll need pigz (pigz n.d.) [🔗](#).

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